

IMPROVING SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT AMONG WOMEN

**Uzbekistan state university of world languages,
Izzatillaeva Ozodakhon Elmurod qizi**

Annotation: This article discusses the improvements done in order to enhance the social life of women today, accommodating conditions suitable for them at the level of state policy in Uzbekistan with accurate numbers. In particular, the establishment of businesses and facilities by the increasing number of women entrepreneurs in all regions of our republic are analyzed.

Keywords: micro environment, macro environment, entrepreneurship centers, social and spiritual environment.

Social environment is the material and spiritual conditions that surround a person both in personal and professional life. The environment in a broad sense (macro environment) is the socioeconomic system - productive forces,

includes a set of social relations and procedures, social consciousness and culture of society. The social environment (micro environment) in the narrow sense is the family, work, education, etc. that surrounds a person directly. Needless to say, social environment has a decisive influence on the formation and development of a person. At the same time, the social environment changes under the influence of human activity and creativity, and in the process of these changes people themselves develop.

A woman is the pillar of family and society, the interest and beauty of our life. With women our lives are beautiful and meaningful, our houses are prosperous and bright. Today and tomorrow of the country are influenced directly by how the importance of women in society and how much are they appreciated, honored and respected. Because society develops and progresses with women's compassion and efforts. That is why in our country to ensure that women are satisfied with their lives, suitable conditions are created and special attention is paid.

In the past short period of time, "state - neighbourhood - people" was used to identify and solve the citizen's problems and an implementation of an effective system of cooperation based on this principle was carried out. The neighborhood acted as a reliable "bridge" between people and the state, supporting families and women with complicated circumstances. At the same time, there are policies ensuring citizens' assemblies are not being burdened,

their cooperation with other subordinate agencies is systematically established, there is a comprehensive system of providing assistance to families, women and the elderly, prevention of early marriages, appropriate measures are taken to solidify social and moral environment in society produce effective results that has positive impact.

It is known that there are five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 to increase the socio-political activity of women and girls in the State programs adopted annually on the basis of the Action Strategy, to strengthen their position in state and community management, to ensure the employment of women, female vocational college graduates are able to expand their entrepreneurial activities. Additionally, to further strengthening of the family foundations, motherhood and childhood protection issues, attention is being paid and many measures have been defined in this regard and consistency of their implementation is being provided. In fact, in recent years, the rights and interests of women in our country, gender equality, protection of family, motherhood and childhood, development of entrepreneurship among women is ensured, creation of new jobs, improvement of working and living conditions has turned into a priority of state policy. Today in our country, men and women have equal rights and the legal framework aimed at creating opportunities and ensuring gender equality has been strengthened.

In our country, women leaders are ministers, governors, heads of industrial associations, banks and companies; the number of our sisters serving in responsible positions in law enforcement agencies and the Armed Forces is increasing. Women are also fully aware of their responsibilities, in whichever field they work, making their proper contribution to the development of the country and the well-being of the people.

It is known that today that the separation of the interests of women from the interests of the family, neighborhood and society is unimaginable.

To improve the social life of women today, to create suitable conditions for them, attention is paid at the level of public policy. In particular, for women in all regions of our republic entrepreneurship centers were established. Today, about 28,000 of our

sisters are given entrepreneurship, crafts, vocational retraining, practical assistance in preventing unemployment. Also, within the framework of five important initiatives, 21,500 girls were trained in short-term vocational courses. The number of women who have started business because of such opportunities increased to nearly 45,000 people in one year, creating thousands of new jobs.

By the departments of the internal affairs serious actions are being taken for the prevention of crimes on women's issues ensuring the stability of the social environment in the neighborhoods, including early prevention of delinquency and crimes among women and fight against various negative diseases in families.

Moreover, a number of activities are being carried out to promote a healthy lifestyle. The self-government bodies of citizens commissions and other organizations are also helping in this endeavor. Let's take the Youth Center in Namangan region. A discussion meeting about regional promotion of improvement of health, care, work among working women was held with the participation of Namangan city and district leaders. At the meeting

duties of the members of the promotion group was further explained.

The role of compact, low-cost facilities in health promotion, work and weddings were mentioned.

To increase the socio-political and social activity of women in our country, solidifying their role in various fields and to ensure their rights, unconditional observance of legal interests, comprehensive support of motherhood and childhood, as well as strengthening of the family institution wide-scale work is being done.

The activity in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution is fundamental for the purpose of improvement, as well as the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Taking into account the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions, the following should be defined as the priorities of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan:

-- firstly, the effective implementation of the state policy to support women provision, protection of their rights and legitimate interests and increase their role and activity in the social and political life of the country;

-- secondly, timely detection of women's problems, providing help and care immediately to those in need, including women with disabilities

giving them sociolegal, psychological and material support;

-- thirdly, ensuring employment of women, improve working conditions, empowering women, especially wide involvement of young girls in rural areas in family and private entrepreneurship, crafts;

-- fourthly, early prevention of crimes among women, first of all,

providing individual work with those who are prone to crime and executing punishment in close cooperation with state bodies and institutions of civil society and ensuring the implementation of measures for the social rehabilitation and adaptation of women released from special institutions.

The Cabinet of Ministers about providing comprehensive help to women in a difficult social situation, disabled, low-income, raising children as a single-parent: the procedure for providing low-cost housing to mothers in need of improvement on the basis of the funds of the Public Fund for Women and Family Support every year in the republic, 10 percent of the initial contribution payments are being paid for houses given to more than a thousand women and girls who live in difficult living conditions, have disabilities, and need housing. In a word, women are always in the state's attention in Uzbekistan. These policies will continue to be executed, because when a woman feels happy, society will be prosperous, the stability of the spiritual environment in the family will be ensured.

REFERENCES:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 2-fevraldagi PF-5325-son Farmoniga 6-ILOVA.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 18-fevraldagi PF-5938-son Farmoniga 2-ILOVA.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 17-martdagi PF-6188-sonli Farmoni tahririda — Qonun hujjatlari ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 17.03.2021-y, 06/21/6188/0216-son).
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 29-noyabrdagi PF-27-sonli Farmoniga asosan o‘z kuchini yo‘qotgan — Qonunchilik ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 01.12.2021-y., 06/21/27/1116-son).

